

INNOVATIVE REFORMS IN THE MODERN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The article talks about the achievements, opportunities gained as a result of the reforms carried out in recent years in the field of preschool education and at the same time the shortcomings allowed in the system, the solutions and proposals aimed at eliminating them. The experiences of the Korean country in the development of the sphere were discussed. The place of higher education in the training of specialists-educators is analytical and critical. Practical proposals were made on the direction of future educators to innovative education.*

Keywords: *educational program "First step", Organization of preschool educations, professor-teacher, teacher, Korean model, teacher-educator, reform, Third Renaissance.*

Today, as science progresses, many scientific research works are being carried out on the basis of exact sciences. However, there is no clear and concise suggestion about education and improvement of the spiritual image of a person. Therefore, education does not always lose its relevance. In all the conducted experiments, it was confirmed that the worldview formed in a person from the youngest age is preserved throughout his life. That is, these are formed as initial competencies and shape the child as a person. When the pedagogue can determine the personal orientation of the child, he can determine the task before him.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev said, "If you ask me what is bothering you, I will answer that it is the education of our children." No matter how many centuries and eras pass, child education is always considered an important duty to parents and teachers. It is important that they not only aim to become a "great" person in the future, but also to mature as a real person, a person who has formed real human qualities in himself. For this, it is necessary to pay great attention to them from a young age and create the most suitable conditions for education.

The introduction of the "Improved First Step" state program into the educational process in preschool educational organizations introduced a new direction in educational activities. The program is structured in a non-traditional way compared to the previous basic programs, and it serves as a method of developing individual abilities of children. Now, the child moves based on his own internal motivation, not on the basis of the teacher's instructions. The child feels that his personality is respected, that his interests and needs are satisfied, that there are conditions for free creative movement.

Forming the essence, goals and tasks of the "Improved First Step" state program in the minds of pedagogues is a time-consuming process. Since the implementation of the program, the working mechanism within it has not yet been completely created. That is why pedagogues-educators have many problems to be solved in order to improve their spiritual, scientific and worldly knowledge. There is a question of providing optimal solutions for pedagogues who are stuck in the old mold and cannot adapt to the new direction. But time is progressing in constant change and development. A specialist who does not constantly work on himself and sharpen his knowledge cannot continue his work in his field. Because the educational system is constantly

changing and improving. This situation is clearly visible in the outlook of the generations of the 21st century. Because today's children are growing up side by side with information and technical resources from a young age. They cannot imagine their daily activities without the virtual world. Therefore, the issue of education requires deep responsibility from parents and teachers.

The laying of the foundation for the Third Renaissance by President Sh. Mirziyoyev motivated everyone to set a new noble goal. Everyone who knows that he is in harmony with the country's destiny strives to contribute to the country's development. Preschool education organizations are the most important base for educating the future generations as well-rounded people who love the country, respect the elders, and feel that they are involved in the development of the country. Taking this into account, we are looking for solutions to the following goals:

- creation of mechanisms for evaluating and improving the knowledge of pedagogues working in the field;
- to determine ways to improve the knowledge of future specialists studying in higher educational institutions;
- development of proposals and recommendations that provide solutions to the problems faced by pedagogues in the implementation of innovative technologies in the educational activities of children of a preschool educational organization.

The reforms applied by many developed foreign countries in the field of preschool education and their effectiveness are studied, and the most appropriate ones are being put into practice. In particular, the Ministry of Preschool Education emphasized the elements of the Korean model. This decision was made after the meetings held during the visits of the head of state to this country. Because within the framework of this visit, during more than 20 meetings and studies, a number of achievements were noticed. The Ministry of Preschool Education has studied the activities of a number of pre-school education organizations in Korea, the created conditions, peculiarities, methods of education, means, the state of financial and material security, and the work being done to protect children's health. The cases of providing quality food were thoroughly studied. As a result, many strategies that can be used in the preschool education system of our country have been developed.

Creation of maximum favorable conditions for the work of pedagogues, creative freedom of the pedagogue, absence of large-scale reports, high social status of pedagogues of state kindergartens, creative environment created for children to express themselves, including comfortable design and equipment of the rooms even down to the smallest details, For them, the availability of rich literature and educational games, social behavior and personal hygiene skills from early childhood are the basis of the success of the Korean preschool education system. [7]

Over the past 2-3 years, the red tape in preschool education organizations has been somewhat optimized. Perfectly standardized criteria were created and applied to the process, from the material and educational base to the quality of food. Educational programs have been created aimed at ensuring more cooperative work of educators-pedagogues with children. However, as a result of the lack of knowledge and lack of work on the part of some officials, they cause excessive confusion during the inspection of educational activities. Therefore, it is necessary to review the requirements for the organization of inspection and control work. It would be expedient if the analysis of activities of pre-school educational organizations is focused on checking the knowledge indicators of more educated students. That is, if it is focused on conducting interviews and evaluation activities with children within the framework of state requirements, the educator-

pedagogue spends a lot of time on preparing documents and on educating children's creative potential. A pedagogue who knows that the supervisor who comes to evaluate the organization will pay attention to the students, always works to expand the worldview of himself and the children.

A teacher-pedagogue should start his work incorporating this content. Children of preschool age have a high level of imitability and attention to the behavior of adults in the environment. Children's psychology is structured in such a way that they want to be encouraged by adults through their every action. Naturally, in order to reach this level, they strive to find in themselves any quality they have. That is, as P.F. Lestgaft said: "The period of kindergarten age is a period in which character traits that will be formed are determined and moral qualities emerge" [6]. Therefore, the spiritual growth of children depends to a large extent on the work of educators. As a result of the teacher's educational activity, the child's worldview can be described as follows.

At the solemn ceremony dedicated to the "Teachers and Mentors" Day, the head of our state said, "We will create the foundations of a new renaissance, that is, the third renaissance, in Uzbekistan through large-scale democratic changes, including educational reforms, we set as our main goal" was the president's speech [9] It can be seen that the prosperity of the new renaissance period will be ensured by the initiative and selfless work of today's teachers-coaches.

Special attention should be paid to the activities of higher education institutions in training future knowledgeable and advanced specialists. The weight of the potential and scientific power of the growing staff depends on the quality of the education they receive today. In the areas of higher education, the network of subjects far from specialization is reduced, and the scope of subjects related to specialization is being expanded. This leads to enrichment and improvement of students' knowledge in their field. At the same time, there are a number of other tasks that await solutions aimed at eliminating them.

We all know that today every parent is in favor of their children learning foreign languages from a young age and actively participating in various circles. Heads of pre-school education organizations naturally want to work together with staff who know one of the foreign languages perfectly. Today, the reason why graduates of higher education institutions have difficulty finding their place in society is their lack of knowledge of foreign languages. Therefore, it is necessary to fundamentally revise the curriculum of preschool education. It takes time to introduce a new mechanism of personnel training in the field. There is a need to specialize preschool education in English or Russian. Because a future specialist who does not know one of these two languages will not find his place in the field. As time passes, this becomes more evident. Therefore, in higher education, if one of the two languages is mastered in depth on the basis of specialized subjects, the personnel potential will increase even more.

Having a creative description of pedagogical activity requires the educator to study advanced work practices, master innovations and put them into practice. The rapid introduction of innovations creates the need to involve educators in scientific research. Involvement of educators in such research work will allow them to successfully use the results obtained later in their work. does not hesitate and achieves high results in creative activities.

In the course of higher education, the professional practice program also needs to be revised. Experience in professional and pedagogical practices is not effective enough. Therefore, it is necessary to enrich the internship program with a new approach. For example, it is recommended to add practice hours to the basis of the specialized subjects of the leading professors

of higher education. For example, while teaching the subject "Innovations in preschool education" to students, the teacher can present innovative educational activities in the environment of preschool education based on his creative potential. This increases the opportunity for the student to gain experience. It also serves as a "Skills lesson" for the employees of the educational organization. That's why it is extremely effective to conduct practice classes together on the basis of each specialty. Also, practicing students can conduct only one open educational activity without preparing various practical documents. It is necessary to have the head of practice and other volunteers participate in such an open training, and at the same time, it is necessary to give the opportunity to conduct another open training based on the student's desire. Then there will be an opportunity to fill in the shortcomings.

For the pedagogues of the preschool education organization, there was a need to reconstruct the entire system of preschool education, to change the methods of communication and interaction not only with the child, but also with all the subjects of preschool education. Therefore, the main task of pedagogues of the preschool organization is to choose the most suitable innovative pedagogical technologies in order to reveal the potential of the individual, the methods and forms of organizing work with children. In order to create an innovative process, the help of leaders-experts will definitely be necessary. Therefore, conducting trainings, consultation hours, and experimental trainings by professors among the employees of pre-school educational organizations gives a very useful result. Therefore, it is necessary to establish cooperation with teachers of higher educational institutions and pedagogues of preschool educational organizations. In such cooperation, pedagogues of preschool education organizations can be involved in higher education seminars. This is useful in sharing experience with students and identifying some shortcomings. As a result of such approaches, it is possible to achieve many achievements in the field.

The goal of the state policy in the field of preschool education is to realize the right of every child to receive quality and free education. The variety of modern system forms of preschool education in Uzbekistan, flexible attitude to the needs of society and the individual, the emergence of new types of preschool education for children being characterized by various pedagogical services. [2. 8 pages] Development indicators in our country can be ensured by quality education and competent individuals. For this, it is necessary that all participants of educational activities do not miss the activity of solidarity in this way.

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